

Figure S1. The sampling location in DR Congo. Blue shad indicates the sampling province in DR Congo.

Figure S2. The phylogenetic tree based on the whole genome sequence of the NDV class II. The tree was constructed in MEGA7 v 7.0.23 using Maximum-Likelihood method based on General Time Reversible model with 1,000 bootstrap replicates. The dataset contains 64 taxa including three Congo strains indicated in red.